

AI technologies evaluation card v0.5

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Introduction

In the wake of growing interest in AI applications for Galleries, Libraries, Archives, and Museums (the GLAM sector), GLAM practitioners and researchers have called for the responsible adoption of AI technologies (Cordell 2020; Padilla 2019). These calls have foregrounded the need for GLAM organisations to address ethical concerns related to AI accuracy, biases, and social and environmental impacts, while also highlighting the opportunity for GLAM organisations to contribute to improving public AI literacy. This document proposes an *AI technologies evaluation card*, which is a transparency artefact intended to enable GLAM organisations to document and publicly share the steps they take to ensure responsible adoption of AI technologies.

The *AI technologies evaluation card* has two objectives. First, informed by Responsible AI principles, the card sets forth a normative framework for holistic AI evaluations in the GLAM sector (i.e. the card outlines what the scope and substance of an AI evaluation should involve). Second, the card provides a template for reporting AI evaluations, intended to provide end users of AI systems deployed by GLAM organisations with the information they need to have confidence in their AI interactions. Here, the card is particularly focused on providing GLAM practitioners and aligned researchers in the Humanities and Social Sciences (HASS) with clarity on the alignment of the AI system with core research values of transparency, openness, reproducibility, and reliability.

The Responsible AI ecosystem

Responsible adoption of AI technologies is a complex problem, requiring a multifaceted approach. Across Cordell (2020), Padilla (2019), and Potter et al. (2022), five streams of work are identified for supporting GLAM organisations to responsibly engage with AI technologies:

1. Responsible adoption can begin with a commitment to responsible use of AI technologies (Padilla 2019), which can be formalized in an ethics statement that articulates the values by which AI use by the GLAM sector will be governed (Cordell 2020), and by which GLAM collections data may be used in AI (Famularo and Denton 2024).
2. Project planning processes and guidelines are then needed to operationalise these values in AI-related projects (Potter et al. 2022), which might include templates for partnerships between cultural sector organisations and developers (Padilla 2019), checklists for the design of AI-related projects (Cordell 2020) and checklists for publication of collections data (Candela et al. 2025; Lee 2025), and standard AI implementation workflows and toolkits (Cordell 2020).
3. Evaluation processes are required to ensure that the values articulated in ethics statements inform AI decisions (Cordell 2020), including decisions about the publication of collections data that may be used in AI training (Famularo and Denton 2024). Such processes may include Algorithmic Impact Assessments (Cordell 2020), auditing of AI models and datasets (Padilla 2019), and frameworks for identifying what users and

organisations have to benefit from AI technologies (Potter et al. 2022) or require of AI systems (Bouich et al. 2025).

4. Complementary accountability structures must be put in place, to ensure that evaluation processes are robust, appropriate, and publicly scrutable (Cordell 2020; Padilla 2019).
5. Finally, across all the previous work streams, capacity and infrastructure building is required. AI literacy and expertise needs to be developed (Cordell 2020; Padilla 2019), and collections data needs to be surfaced in ways that enable AI experimentation and use (Cordell 2020). To support this, a maturity model for AI engagement may be needed (Manchester 2023).

The *AI technologies evaluation card* sits across the third and fourth work streams listed. As a series of prompts, the card can be used to design holistic evaluations of AI technologies. As a template, the card can be used to as part of public-facing accountability efforts.

Principles to guide evaluations

The *AI technologies evaluation card* is designed to align with the HASTRICT principles, which themselves are designed to be consistent with more general Responsible AI principles. Where an evaluation design addresses all the components of the *AI technologies evaluation card*, and the card is used to report the design and findings of the evaluation, it is likely that the evaluation will reflect the HASTRICT principles.

The AI technologies evaluation card: explication

Evaluation attribution

As with any research output, the evaluation should be attributable and dated.

Evaluation goal and hypotheses

The evaluation goal defines what the purpose of an evaluation is – i.e. what those who designed the evaluation hoped to learn through the evaluation exercise. The evaluation goal will usually be formatted as a statement of intent or research question.

The goal should be accompanied by one or more hypotheses that record the evaluation designers' predictions or expected outcome of the evaluation exercise. Hypotheses should be testable, declarative statements.

Setting evaluation scope

Scope sets the boundaries of an evaluation and must be defined prior to an evaluation exercise being designed. Aspects of AI technologies (e.g. specific components, or a particular AI system) that are defined as in-scope will be the target of an evaluation – i.e. the relationship between these aspects and the evaluation hypotheses will be the focus of the evaluation.

Due to the highly networked nature of AI technologies, and their presentation as general-purpose tools, defining the scope of an evaluation can be challenging. Generally, we recommend aiming to evaluate AI technologies for specific use cases in specific settings. This approach is likely to produce an evaluation design that is far more practical for GLAM organisations.

To support scope setting, we distinguish between three ways of framing the scope of an evaluation: performance, compliance, and effectiveness. Across these different frames, we differentiate between two evaluation target options: decomposed or composed evaluations. These options are presented in Table 1 below. Note that any scope setting exercise will need to involve trade-offs; a truly holistic assessment of an AI system will likely involve a sequence of several different evaluations, with each evaluation documented in a separate evaluation card.

Table 1. Scope options

	Evaluation framing		
Evaluation target	Performance Scope of evaluation is set as assessing performance of AI technologies against defined measures or benchmarks (e.g. accuracy, fairness).	Compliance Scope of evaluation is set as assessing compliance of an AI technology with organisational or regulatory policies (e.g. privacy policy, Indigenous Data Sovereignty policy).	Effectiveness Scope of evaluation is set as assessing the effectiveness of an AI technology, in terms of a particular use case and setting.
Decomposed Evaluation targets a component of an AI system or comparison of specific components (e.g. an AI model, a training dataset).	Narrowest scope (evaluation may be automated)		
Composed Evaluation targets a complete AI system or comparison of different standalone AI systems (e.g. ChatGPT vs Claude).			Broadest scope (evaluation will need to involve system users)

Defining evaluation target

The target for an evaluation is the specific AI system and/or components that will be the focus of the evaluation. These are determined by the scope of the evaluation but need to be transparently reported in sufficient detail to enable end-users to replicate evaluation settings as far as possible. Even in instances where an evaluation is very narrowly scoped (e.g. focused on only performance of an AI model), the evaluation target is likely to include several AI system components, to enable interaction and interpretation of the model.

For each component within the evaluation target, the following details need to be provided:

- Precise component version (e.g. ‘claude-sonnet-4-20250514’, rather than ‘Claude Sonnet 4’)
- Access link for component (e.g. ideally, link to where component can be downloaded)
- Notes on any component dependencies (e.g. requirement to have Claude account and credits)

Alongside the above details, the evaluation target itself should be associated with a unique identifier, should include an interactive worked example (e.g. a Jupyter Notebook) and component diagrams, and should be containerized to enable any end-user to replicate the evaluation target on their own device.

Evaluation participants (if any)

For evaluations that involve user testing, participant information should be recorded, including the sample size, participant recruitment strategy, and inclusion criteria. General demographic information, alongside any information that might be relevant to participants’ observations regarding the evaluation should be recorded. In many AI evaluations this is likely to include information regarding participants’ professional background, specialist expertise, and prior exposure to AI technologies.

Evaluation metrics

As determined by the scope of the evaluation, the specific metrics through which an AI system or component will be evaluated should be listed. The link between these metrics, the underlying goal or hypothesis of the evaluation, and the evaluation exercise should be made explicit. Table 2 provides an example.

Table 2. Evaluation metrics

Underlying goal or hypothesis	Metric	Measurement tool
LLMs can accurately generate annotation data for historical images	Accuracy	Comparison of LLM-generated annotation data with existing expert-provided annotation data

Evaluation design and harness

The detailed design of the evaluation should be reported, including the harness used to instantiate the evaluation. All necessary information for a third party to reproduce the evaluation should be included.

Evaluation limitations

Finally, any potential limitations inherent in the evaluation design or set up should be reported. Particular attention should be paid to the potential for the AI system under evaluation to be repurposed for tasks that are different to those which were evaluated.

Evaluation lessons

Given the purpose of an evaluation is to learn something about an AI system or component, these lessons should be reported in the evaluation card. Lessons should be captured as recommendations for potential users and developers of the AI system or components that were evaluated.

The AI technologies evaluation card: template

Table 3. Example evaluation card

<p><i>Evaluation attribution</i> Berman, Glen. Smithies, James. 2025. "Evaluation of LLM+RAG systems for use in historical research." HASS Digital Research Hub, Australian National University. zenodo.org/communities/aiinfra.</p>	
<p>Part 1: Evaluation scope</p>	
<p><i>1A. Evaluation goal</i> Goal: to evaluate whether LLM+RAG systems are fit for purpose for use by historians</p>	<p><i>1B. Evaluation hypotheses</i> Hypothesis 1: that LLM+RAG systems can aid in identification of patterns or themes across large datasets of primary historical materials Hypothesis 2: that LLM+RAG systems can accurately summarise primary historical materials</p>
<p><i>1C. Evaluation scope</i> <i>In scope</i>¹</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Different publicly available LLMs • Different RAG set ups, including vectorization, word embedding, and search strategies 	<p><i>Out of scope</i>²</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Comparison across different historical datasets • Analysis of historical datasets in language other than English • Impact of user interface design on use of LLM+RAG systems • Environment impact of LLM+RAG systems • Cost to end-users of LLM+RAG systems
<p>Part 2: Evaluation details</p>	
<p><i>2A. Evaluation target</i>³ Target summary:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Name: k20_claude4_bert_1000 • Details, including diagram and downloadable version available at: zenodo.org/communities/aiinfra <p>Target details:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • LLM: claude-sonnet-4-20250514 • System prompt: You are a 1901 Hansard parliamentary records expert (Australia, New Zealand, United Kingdom). Provide well-structured responses of 200-300 words using only the provided context. Write in clear, academic prose with proper paragraph structure. Include key details, quotes, and evidence to address parliamentary questions effectively. FILTERED queries (single country selected): Focus exclusively on that country's records. UNFILTERED queries (all countries): Compare and contrast across UK, Australia, and New Zealand. Highlight similarities, differences, and interactions between parliamentary approaches. Off-topic questions: redirect to 1901 parliamentary topics. Use ONLY the provided context documents. Provide thorough, evidence-based responses. Start with a direct answer, then elaborate with relevant evidence and examples. Include specific details, member names, dates, and parliamentary procedures when available. If context is insufficient: ask for question refinement. Off-topic: redirect briefly to 1901 parliamentary topics. Write naturally - citations auto-generated. Integrate 	

¹ List of AI aspects that are within the scope of the evaluation (i.e. the specific AI components or systems whose relationship to the listed hypotheses will be evaluated).

² List any AI aspects that have been intentionally set as outside of the scope of the evaluation, but that may be relevant to future evaluations.

³ Brief description of evaluation target and link to worked example and containerized version.

<p>multiple sources seamlessly. Context-only responses. No external knowledge. No unsupported claims. Repository stats: use only manifest.json data. Content questions: use context documents only. Acknowledge uncertainty explicitly. Maintain context in follow-ups. Insufficient context: suggest more specific questions. Guide better formulation, not technical limitations. Provide comprehensive, well-researched answers using the provided parliamentary documents. Structure responses clearly and include sufficient detail to fully address the research question.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • RAG details: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Vector Store: blert_1000 <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Created: 2025-08-23T22:31:28.482229Z ▪ Embedding model: Livingwithmachines/bert_1890_1900 ▪ DB size: 1,018 MB ▪ Totals: files 206, chunks 94,936, words 12,738,700, chars 73,803,394 ▪ Corpora: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 1901_au: files 113, chunks 40,756, words 4,679,284 • 1901_uk: files 31, chunks 30,677, words 4,040,154 • 1901_nz: files 62, chunks 23,503, words 4,019,262 ▪ Metadata fields: 8 (enums: corpus) ○ Vector search type and algorithm: similarity, HNSW ○ Retrieval size: 120 (single corpus), 80 (all corpus) ○ Search K: 20 ○ Search score threshold: 0 ○ Chunk size: 1000 ○ Chunk overlap: 200 ○ Pooling: mean+max ○ Multi corpus vector store: true 											
<p>2B. Evaluation participants</p> <table border="0" style="width: 100%;"> <tr> <td style="width: 33%;"> <p>Sample size: 7</p> </td> <td style="width: 33%;"> <p>Recruitment strategy: Direct outreach</p> </td> <td style="width: 33%;"> <p>Inclusion criteria: Postgraduate students in a history course</p> </td> </tr> <tr> <td> <p>Details of participants: 3 students based at an Australian research university, 4 students based in UK research universities</p> </td> <td> <p>Participants' expertise: All participants have expertise in analysis of primary materials; 4 participants have additional expertise in Hansard data</p> </td> <td> <p>Participants' prior exposure to AI technologies: Minimal.</p> </td> </tr> </table>			<p>Sample size: 7</p>	<p>Recruitment strategy: Direct outreach</p>	<p>Inclusion criteria: Postgraduate students in a history course</p>	<p>Details of participants: 3 students based at an Australian research university, 4 students based in UK research universities</p>	<p>Participants' expertise: All participants have expertise in analysis of primary materials; 4 participants have additional expertise in Hansard data</p>	<p>Participants' prior exposure to AI technologies: Minimal.</p>			
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<p>2D. Evaluation design and harness</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Participants were asked to rate the quality of LLM+RAG outputs based on 10 questions • Participants used the ATLAS Hansard harness to review LLM+RAG outputs and rate questions • Participants' engagement was limited to 30 minutes • Further details available at: zenodo.org/communities/aiinfra. 	<p>2E. Evaluation limitations</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Evaluation focused only on one LLM model and one LLM+RAG set up. • Although participants were trained in historical analysis, they were not subject matter experts in Hansard data. 										
<p>Part 3: Evaluation lessons</p>											
<p>3A. Recommendations for AI implementers</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • To come. 	<p>3B. Recommendations for AI end-users</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • To come. 										

References

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